

DETERMINANTS OF ENGAGEMENT AMONG INSTAGRAM USERS TOWARDS INSTAGRAM FASHION INFLUENCERS

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ABSTRACT

Influencer marketing seems to be a trend today, but consumers are not receptive to it; they tend to unfollow the influencers' Instagram account. The number of followers on social media is a way to measure the influencer's influence on others. Earning followers on social media is essential and challenging, but it is also the same as retaining them. Maintaining a social profile is not that seamless as people would always either follow or unfollow the influencer. This study aims to examine and discuss the factors that affect the engagement intention of Malaysian Instagram users towards Instagram fashion influencers. To achieve this goal, the researcher proposes a conceptual model that combines the Theory of Planned Behavior. Three variables influenced Instagram users' intention to engage with Instagram fashion influencers, attitude, social norms, and perceived behavioral control. The intention of users will then positively influence their engagement behavior. A quantitative method was applied, whereby online questionnaires were distributed to obtain data from Malaysians with an Instagram account and follow at least one Instagram fashion influencer. A total of 225 respondents have completed the questionnaire, but only 174 were eligible. Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) was used to analyze the data collected. The result presented that attitude, social norms positively influence intention to engage and perceived behavioral control. Hence, this is directly influenced positively on actual engagement with the Instagram influencers. The research findings will give future researchers a better insight into social media users' engagement with social media influencers. Also, the findings will help marketers, and Instagram influencers in the fashion industry understand the elements that influence Instagram users to engage with Instagram fashion influencers.

Keywords: User engagement, Instagram, Instagram influencers, Theory of Planned Behaviour